

Volume 2

No 3

January 2017

ISSN : 2454 - 4531

AKCE QUEST

Quarterly Journal

ARULMIGU KALASALINGAM COLLEGE OF EDUCATION

(Accredited by NAAC at B Grade with a CGPA of 2.87 on a four point scale)

Krishnankoil-626 126, Srivilliputtur (Taluk), Virudhunagar District

IMPACT OF CLASSROOM ENVIRONMENT ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

Dr. N. Subramanian

Abstract

An educator, Richard Reginald Green, supports the preceding concept when he said, "The future of the nation is on the shoulders of teachers and how they teach kids; the future of the world is in the classroom where the teachers are. And if we have any chance to guarantee a positive bridge to the 21st century, it is how we educate the children in the classroom today." Teachers are the catalysts of change; they are the torch bearers always lighting the path towards progress of the world in all its facets. The classroom still remains to be the main learning environment in the schools although learning can take place in other venues. On this premise, it is imperative that educators strive to make the classroom the best venue for students to attain their full potential in academic performance. The goal of this study is to see if students' perceptions of their classroom environment are related to their academic achievement. It is hypothesized that there is a relationship between the classroom environment and academic achievement of higher secondary students. The sample was 150 higher secondary students selected through stratified random technique from Tenkasi Educational District. The instrument used to measure the level of classroom climate as perceived by the students was an adaptation of the downloaded classroom climate questionnaire. For measuring academic achievement of higher secondary students, the investigator used the scores of them in all the subjects in quarterly examination. Pearson's r set at 0.05 level of significance was used for inferential statistics. With the p -value=.000 which is lesser than 0.05 level of significance, academic performance is significantly correlated to classroom climate. Classroom climate to a certain extent has some influence on academic performance of students.

Introduction

An educator, Richard Reginald Green, supports the preceding concept when he said, "The future of the nation is on the shoulders of teachers and how they teach kids; the future of the world is in the classroom where the teachers are. And if we have any chance to guarantee a positive bridge to the 21st century, it is how we educate the children in the classroom today." Teachers are the catalysts of change; they are the torch bearers always lighting the path towards progress of the world in all its facets. The classroom still remains to be the main learning environment in the schools although learning can take place in other venues. On this premise, it is imperative that educators strive to make the classroom the best venue for students to attain their full potential in academic performance. According to Andy Hargreaves and Michael Fullon, "It is what teachers think, what teachers do and what teachers are at the level of the classroom that ultimately shapes the kind of learning that young people get."

Classroom Environment

Classroom

A classroom or schoolroom is a room dedicated primarily to teaching or learning activities. Classroom is found in educational institutions of all kinds, including public and private schools, home schools, corporations, and religious and humanitarian organizations. The classroom attempts to provide a safe space where learning can take place uninterrupted by other distractions.

Assistant Professor, S Veerasamy Chettiar College of Education
Puliangudi-627 855, Tirunelveli District

Environment

Built environment, constructed surroundings that provide the setting for human activity, ranging from the large-scale civic surroundings to the personal places. Environment (biophysical), the physical and biological factors along with their chemical interactions that affect an organism.

Classroom Environment

Throughout the world, most teaching takes place in classrooms. These classrooms are typically inhabited by 20 or more students and a single adult, the teacher (Anderson, et. Al, 1989). The ratio of one teacher to 20 or more students results in natural imbalance between teaching and learning. When teacher teaches in classrooms, they must by necessity, direct a great deal of their teaching to groups of students. Even when they work with individual students, they must be aware of what other students in the group or class are going. What students learn from this predominantly group-oriented teaching, on the other hand depends to a large extent on the unique characteristics brought to classrooms by the individual students. The best predictor of what students know and can do at the end of some period of schooling is the knowledge and skills with which they entered that period of schooling. Classroom environment encompasses a broad range of educational concepts, including the physical setting, the psychological environment created through social contexts, and numerous instructional components related to teacher characteristics and behaviors.

Academic Achievement

Good's dictionary defines it as "Achievement test is a test designed to measure a persons knowledge, skills, understandings, etc., in a given field taught in school" According to Collin's Dictionary "A test designed to measure the effects that learning and teaching have on individuals is called an achievement test". Academic achievement may also refer to a person's strong performance in a given academic arena. Academic achievement is nothing but educational attainment, which refers to the gains, got by the pupils as a result of education.

Population of the Study

The populations of the present study are all the students studying in standard XI and XII in the higher secondary Schools in Tenkasi Educational District.

Sample of the Study

The investigator has selected 150 higher secondary students from 10 higher secondary schools from the population. For selecting the students, the investigation used random sampling method.

Instrument and Statistical Tools

The instrument used to measure the level of classroom climate as perceived by the students was an adaptation of the downloaded classroom climate questionnaire. For measuring academic achievement of higher secondary students, the investigator used the scores of them in all the subjects in quarterly examination. Pearson's r set at 0.05 level of significance was used for inferential statistics.

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between classroom environment and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

Significance of the Study

Education in India is recognized as an important investment in human capital. It contributes to socioeconomic development by providing people with skills, knowledge, capability and attitudes for productive work. As a result, a substantial proportion of the country's resources has been allocated to education. Since the benefits of education are perceived as pervasive, it is understandable why people talk

about education and not about classrooms because they expect that conditions can be arranged at the school level and that the effects of these can spread out through the whole system, the school and classes. Education is provided in the classroom. The classroom is the nucleus where other factors influencing the students' learning and their educational outcomes are found like classmates, teachers and textbooks. In fact, all the factors that contribute to educational outcomes exist in one way or another in the classroom. Classrooms can be viewed as places in which teachers, students and subject matters interact. It is intuitively plausible that the teacher is a key figure in the kinds of relationships that prevail in his or her classroom. It is also likely that the teacher's attitudes resulting from his or her life experience will have a noticeable effect on the kind of relationships, which this teacher creates, in his or her classroom. The strength of an education system must largely depend upon the quality of its teachers because teachers are the point of contact between the educational system and students. Perhaps the students have benefited from the learning environment that is comfortable and safe. The nature of the classroom environment greatly influences students' character development and intellectual readiness to learn. Classroom is the place where students see as their "home" at school. Students' well being also depends on the classroom, classmates, teachers, and the activities in the classrooms. Classroom environment encompasses a broad range of educational concepts, including the physical setting, the psychological environment created through social contexts, and numerous instructional components related to teacher characteristics and behaviors. The physical environment in the classrooms has continued to appear in contemporary studies as an influence on behavioral and academic outcomes. Overcrowded facilities, too many students in certain classes, and lack of teachers' assistants are three major issues cited as potentially creating problems due to increased stress levels of students and increased teacher-reported incidences of behavioral problems. These increased stress levels and behavior problems found in larger classrooms are frequently accompanied by lower levels of academic achievement. In this connection, this study provides a valuable reference for other schools to reflect upon the classroom environment as it affect the academic performance of students in higher secondary school at higher secondary level.

Inferential Analysis

H₀: 1 There is no significant relationship between classroom environment and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

Table 1
Pearson Correlation Test Showing the Relationship between Classroom Environment and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary Students

Correlation	N	Calculated "r" value	Table "r" value	Remarks at 5% level of significance
Relationship between classroom environment and academic achievement of higher	150	0.19	0.17	S

(at 5% level of significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated "r" value (0.19) is greater than the table value (0.17) for N (150) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus there is significant relationship between classroom environment and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

Interpretation

There is significant relationship between classroom environment and academic achievement of higher secondary students. Overcrowded facilities, too many students in certain classes, and lack of teachers' assistants are three major issues cited as potentially creating problems due to increased stress levels of students and increased teacher-reported incidences of behavioral problems. These increased

stress levels and behavior problems found in larger classrooms are frequently accompanied by lower levels of academic achievement. Beyond the physical arrangement of a classroom a psychological environment is also created, based on the interaction of key players in the classroom, namely students and teachers. Research in this area has varied greatly and proliferated during the early twenty-first century. Studies have been particularly concentrated on student class participation rates, teacher support, and communication of learning goals. Today all formal education takes place in the manmade environment of schools and classrooms. The buildings should thus be conducive to the teaching and learning process. Lack of proper infrastructure has been a major concern area for many years. Quality standards of schools in terms of infrastructure, often do not meet the parameters laid down in the Education Bill of the government.

Conclusion

The research revealed that a significant positive correlation exists between classroom climate and academic achievement of higher secondary students. So the classroom environment plays a crucial role in keeping students engaged and allowing them to be successful within the classroom. Students experience the classroom as not just an intellectual space, but also as a social, emotional, and physical environment. Classrooms that subtly or indirectly exclude certain groups of students tend to be common from the students' perspectives. Instructors' attentiveness to the intellectual, social, emotional, and physical environments creates a classroom climate conducive to student engagement with the content and skills of the discipline. In terms of the intellectual environment, instructors provide content in an organized and engaging manner and give students motivating and challenging practice so that they are able to do authentic tasks in the discipline. From the emotional aspect of classroom climate, instructors create an encouraging atmosphere where students feel safe taking risks, receive support when events intrude on learning, and believe they can succeed if they put forth effort. And instructors foster approachable and supportive social interactions with students and among students so that learning is a collaborative and not competitive endeavor. With respect to the physical environment, instructors reduce and remove disruptions and barriers to learning so that all students can equally access course material.

References

1. Ameetha P (2005). "*Methods of Teaching Biological Science*" Neelkamal Publications, Hyderabad - 500 095.
2. Bajpai Singh (2007). "*Research Methodology Techniques and Trends*" APH Publishing Corporation, New Delhi.
3. Chaube S.P. & A. Chaube (2005). "*School Organisation*" Vikas Publications House Pvt Ltd. New Delhi.
4. Rao and Khadar (2005). "*School Education in India*", Discovery Publishing House, New Delhi.
http://www.dlsu.edu.ph/conferences/dlsu_research_congress/2014/_pdf/proceedings/LLI-I-003-FT.pdf